

12th International Manikin and Modelling Meeting
29-31 August 2018, St. Gallen, Switzerland

Design of female protective jacket: wearer-centric approach

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.1404497

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Introduction

Modernisation of the fire and rescue services, police, the defence forces, and building and construction worldwide has increased expectations about diversity in the workforce and women having easy access to and success in these and other sectors [1–5]. Women are increasingly actively engaging in these traditionally masculine occupations and roles, including some requiring personal protective equipment (PPE). Research suggests that properly fitting work clothing improves the efficacy and job satisfaction of female workers in male-dominated occupations [6,7]. Providing a gender-diverse workforce with the best protective and performance-enabling equipment requires an innovative body-centric design approach. We investigated the effects of differences in body geometry on air gap volumes under male firefighters' jackets and their thermophysiological comfort attributes using body scanning technology, the thermal instrumental manikin Newton (male and female), and subjective evaluation by a female volunteer. The results underpinned the design of a new prototype female firefighters' jacket, which was shown to have improved performance attributes.

Methods

The experimental study involved standard-issue Australian firefighters' protective jackets. The male firefighters' protective jacket used in this study is a three-layered garment comprising a structural fire coat with removable inner liner designed and manufactured by Australian Defence Apparel (Victoria, Australia). The inner and middle layer are stitched together, while the outer layer is a removable fire coat made of a blend of polybenzimidazole and Kevlar® fibres and provides protection from fire and radiative heat. The middle layer is comprised of a Crosstech® moisture barrier membrane with added heat-stable and chemically inert spacer Airlock® technology. The inner layer of the jacket is a thin and light Nomex® woven fabric. Very similar jackets are also commonly used internationally. First, we investigated the effects of differences in human body geometry on air gap volumes in the next-to-skin microclimate under male jackets and on their attributes relevant to thermophysiological comfort. Three-dimensional (3D) body scanning technology and a thermal instrumental manikin Newton was used in male and female body form for this purpose. In addition, a subjective evaluation of the jackets on a female volunteer was carried out, and the results of objective and subjective evaluations combined to underpin the design of a new prototype female jacket. The prototype was constructed from the same materials as the male jackets, was constructed to fit to the female form, to meet the required protection standards, and was evaluated objectively and subjectively. The female jacket conformed to the protective requirements. A 2×2 factorial design analysis was applied to compare the influence of body geometry and different jacket sizes on microclimate air volume.

Results

The total air volume of the next-to-skin microclimate under male jackets of both small and medium sizes worn on the female form manikin was higher than that for the jackets worn on the male form. The microclimate volume under the small jacket was 13% greater on the female than the male form ($p < 0.001$) and 15% greater ($p < 0.001$) under the medium jacket. The factorial design analysis of mean air volume for the two different human body forms and two jacket sizes indicated that both factors – body form and jacket size – significantly influence the microclimate air volume ($p < 0.001$). The highest permeability index (I_m) was recorded for the male manikin dressed in the small jacket; I_m was slightly lower for the medium jacket when worn on the male manikin form. The objective evaluation was followed by the subjective evaluation. The volunteer wears medium-sized everyday clothing, but chose the small male jacket for the trials as it fit better; she reported that the medium size was very loose and restricted movement. However, she found the small jacket too long on both the body and sleeves. After the stepping exercise the volunteer

reported an overall uncomfortable sensation (especially around her neck and wrists) in normal conditions, and was very uncomfortable overall in hot conditions.

The new female jacket was designed using the data acquired from objective and subjective experiments. The new design and construction took into consideration the requirements of safety standard AS/NZS 4967:2009. Total microclimate air volume was substantially reduced, which resulted in significantly better Im (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Im for Small male jacket and new female jacket on female manikin body form.

The results of the objective evaluations of the new female jacket were in agreement with its subjective evaluation. The new female jacket had 'perfect' fit: it was neither too loose nor too tight, both overall and at all sites of the wearer's body. The overall comfort rating of the jacket was the same for the normal and hot conditions, and for hot conditions improved from 1 ('very uncomfortable') to 4 (with 5 being 'comfortable').

Conclusions

The study determined that the microclimate air volume is significantly larger under male jackets when worn on the female than the male body. In addition, the lowest permeability indexes were found for male jackets worn on the female body form. The study showed that both body form and jacket size significantly influence the microclimate air volume. The results of the subjective evaluation agreed with the objective evaluation. The research demonstrated the effectiveness of an innovative body-centric approach to the design of PPE intended to be worn by women workers engaged in traditionally male-dominated fields.

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